

The Speech Structure is the Semantic Structure of the Expression

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Abstract:

In the article, researchers tend to distinguish the sentence as the main linguistic unit necessary to convey a message. A sentence is a primary speech event with a holistic content. Along with the main nominative and predicative meaning fragments, many specific additional meaning fragments are also expressed within the speech activity. The emergence of these additional meanings is reflected in the context of communication, a certain environment, and the author's opinions and scientific analytical research are highlighted.

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The complex interrelationship of objective and subjective features of each speech act ensures the multifacetedness of the speech structure. In addition to the main nominative and predicative meaning fragments, many unique additional meaning fragments are also expressed within this relationship. The appearance of these additional meanings is related to the context of communication, a certain environment. In this, the social status of the speaker and the listener, and personal characteristics take their place. Many of the additional meanings mentioned are connotative and are understood through context. According to Uzbek linguists, "the hidden statement of the expression, the meaning of the sentence is inextricably linked with the thinking activity of the communication participants and their perceptions of the world. The wider the speaker's perception of the external world, the faster he understands the level of the speech situation. That is why it is related to the inner goal of the speaker to openly or covertly express the information views in the semantic structure of the expression, to give the information view that cannot be expressed openly in the form of meaning" (Hakimov, Gazieva 2020: 73).

The additional, sometimes colorful meaning of a linguistic unit is often associated with the concept of "connotation" in linguistics. The term connotation is derived from the Latin word *connotare* - "additional expression", and linguistics borrowed it from the science of logic. This term was originally applied to vocabulary items. In the comments given in special dictionaries, it is emphasized that connotation refers to the emotional-expressive properties of language units together with the semantic-stylistic status.

Including D. In Kristal's dictionary we read the following comment: "A term used on semantics as a part of a classification of types of meaning; opposed to denotation. Its main application is with reference to the emotional associations (personal or communal) which are suggested by, or are part of the meaning of a linguistic unit, especially a lexical item..." (Crystal 2008:102).

A. In the explanatory dictionary of linguistic terms compiled by Hojiev, the concept of connotation is contrasted with the concept of denotation: "The connotative meaning of a language unit (expression of additional meaning or meanings such as expressive, stylistic relation)" (Hojiev 2002:51-52).

I. V. Arnold's "Stylistics In the book " *sovremennogo angliyskogo yaz yka* ", the content of the concept of " connotation " is divided into four parts. These are : expressiveness, emotionality, evaluation and functional-methodical coloring (Arnold 1990 :7).

The functional-stylistic connotation intended for the communication environment serves to give the speech structure the spirit of solemnity, grandeur, formality, freedom, closeness, perfection, lyricism. This kind of colorfulness of speech is achieved through the formal and spiritual harmony of units belonging to a single functional-stylistic layer or the involvement of elements specific to other styles into the sphere of speech activity that is foreign to them. The methodological layer of the context gives impetus to the occurrence of this kind of " game of connotations " . At the same time, the speech structure has contradictory stylistic indicators. It is clear that these types of connotations play an important role in figurative artistic speech. Compare :

Hear and attend and listen; for this befell and be happened and became and was, O my Best Beloved, when the tame animals were wild. (R. Kipling. *The Cat that walked by Himself*).

My mother used to pour tea to the neighbors in a cup with flowers, and she would brag about it :

➤ My daughter gave it! Look, I have such a daughter, look at how I am not a fool! If you call it gardens, it is a white house! Double rugs! It has a radio, it comes in a box. If you see my daughter's agility. Some rice and some meat came down, and the soup was boiling as if it had been filled with seeds. You won't tell my husband, he is the head of the *peravodni*. That oil is *Ashgabat*, this oil is *Leninabad* - there is no place in seven climates that has not been seen. One is polite, one is smart... (O'. *Hoshimov*. *I found my sister*).

In the example from the English language, we see that the connotation of solemnity is formed by means of an archaic vocabulary unit and syntactic repetition.

But it is not necessary to chain elements with different stylistic colors in order to create a functional-stylistic connotation. The presence of a separate high-level element is enough for the speech structure to acquire a stylistic connotation. For example, in the following speech structure, the spirit of content is achieved through the use of the uncountable noun in the plural form:

All my struggles for many years were wasted (WS *Maugham*).

Connotation, which fulfills the purpose of naming the value, is related to assigning a certain value to any object. Such an axiological assessment takes place in the modal content of the speech structure (N.A. *Avganova* 1985).

The evaluation structure usually expresses the attitude of the speaker towards the object and expresses the evaluation given to a certain person or thing. For example, in the following case, the speaker negatively evaluates the behavior of the interlocutor's son, emphasizes that he needs a father (even if he is a stepfather) and indicates that the boy is a man:

"Don't you want him to have a father" Daniel asked. "God knows he needs one. He's terribly spoiled" (M. Dickens).

In this speech structure, the connotation of evaluation is formed within its basic meaning and is not directly expressed in the speaker's statement.

In the following excerpt from the short story "Momokoshiq" written by Nazar Eshanqul, we can see that the connotation of evaluation is directly expressed:

"Don't pay attention to them," he whispered in Shamsi Salah's ear. —If you pay attention to everything, you will have a heart attack. These are not yet completely freed from wildness. Shamsi Salah realized that he wanted to say "from an animal" and, in a mockery of himself, he said "from a wild animal" (Nazar Eshanqul. The smell of mint).

Predicative-connotation is contrasted with the nominative-connotation fragments involved in the semantic structure of the sentence. These connotative meaning fragments connect the situation described in the discourse structure with reality.

Interpersonal communication or phatic connotations allow the listener to join the communication process (Drazdauskane 1976) and draw his attention to the speaker's thoughts, encouraging him to continue the communication. Among the phatic fragments of the meaning, the expressions of sympathy, agreeing with the listener's opinion stand out. For example :

"You must come again when we're a little more up to the mark," added the nurse. "It's a pity you came at such a time," "for we're not quite ourselves today, are we dear?" (Ch. Chaplin).

In this case, the connotations of sympathy and trust are vividly expressed in the nurse's speech. This is achieved by expanding the meaning of the pronoun we, that is, it also refers to the second and third persons.

The connotation of intention related to the speaker's communicative purpose occurs within the meaning of urging the listener to a certain action. If the speaker's direct intention manifested by means of a speech act expresses the content of giving an order or encouraging the listener to respond, when performing connotative speech acts, pragmatic meanings such as request, advice, and suggestion are indirectly manifested. This type of use of speech structures is described in the scope of indirect speech acts in the field of pragmalinguistics (Austin 1986 ; Searle 1986; Hakimov 2020; Shomahmudova 2022).

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